

Leaching and drying of neem flakes to obtain a botanical insecticide

Lakning och torkning av neemflingor för att erhålla ett botaniskt insektsmedel

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Summary

This thesis was carried out at the Department of Chemical Engineering at the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH) in Stockholm, Sweden. The experimental part was performed at “Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería” (UNI) in Managua, Nicaragua. The work is part of a co-operation program between the two universities, financed by the Swedish International Development Agency, Sida. The stay in Managua was partly financed by Sida through their Minor Field Study scholarship.

In Nicaragua, agriculture is the main contributor to the gross national product. Synthetically obtained insecticides have been used extensively, which has provoked negative affects on both human health and the environment. A natural insecticide can be extracted from the fruit seeds of a tree called neem, which is growing in plantations in Nicaragua. The neem seed contains oil and a mixture of different substances with insecticide properties. Processing of the neem seeds to obtain the insecticide has been performed before in a batch-wise process using ground neem seeds leached in agitated tanks and in a two-step process using flakes of neem seeds leached in columns. In the first step oil is leached with hexane and in the second step insecticide compounds is leached with ethanol.

The purpose of this thesis is to experimentally study the feasibility of improving the processing of neem flakes in columns by performing the leaching of insecticide without intermediate removal of the non-polar solvent and by performing simultaneously both leaching steps. Methanol is used instead of ethanol, since hexane and ethanol are miscible and would make the solvent separation after leaching difficult. The drying of the solvents remaining in the neem flakes is also experimentally studied.

The parameters chosen to be studied in the leaching part of this thesis is leaching time, thickness of the flakes, volume ratio of solvents, and total volume of solvents. They were all shown to have a great influence on the yield of insecticide components, but the influence of solvent ratio was the most important one. It was shown that more methanol than hexane had to be used to obtain a large yield of insecticide compounds. The yield of oil was mainly influenced of the flake thickness.

Leaching with the polar- non polar solvent mixture compared to the batch-wise process and the two-step process, results in a higher yield of insecticide compounds in a shorter total process time, using flake thickness of 2 mm. For the smaller flake thickness, 0.7 mm, 2 percent units lower yield of insecticide compounds were reached in half the total process time of the two-step process.

In the drying part of the thesis obvious conclusions are difficult to make. What can be said is that the temperature of the incoming air flow has influence on the process. A higher temperature results in shorter drying time and faster drying rate at certain moisture content. Conclusions about the drying time or the drying rate are not possible to make from the results of the experiments. The variations in drying time are too large and the drying rate seems to be independent of the conditions of the previous leaching step.

Sammanfattning

Det här arbetet utfördes på Institutionen för Kemiteknik vid Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan (KTH) i Stockholm, Sverige. Den experimentella delen utfördes vid "Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería" (UNI) i Managua, Nicaragua. Arbetet är del av ett samarbetsprogram mellan dessa två universitet, finansierat av Swedish International Development Agency, Sida. Vistelsen i Managua finansierades delvis av Sida genom stipendiet Minor Field Study.

I Nicaragua är jordbruket den största bidragaren till bruttonationalprodukten. Syntetiska insektsmedel har använts i stor omfattning, vilket har orsakat negativa effekter på både människor och miljö. Ett naturligt insektsmedel kan extraheras ur fruktkärnor från ett träd kallat neem, som växer på plantage i Nicaragua. Neemkärnorna innehåller olja och en blandning av ämnen med egenskaper liknande insektsmedel. Bearbetning av neemkärnorna för att erhålla insektsmedlet har utförts tidigare i en sats-vis process med neemkärnor som lakades i omrörda tankar och i en två-stegs process med flingor av neemkärnor som lakades i kolonner. I ett första steg lakas oljan med hexan och i ett andra lakas insektsmedelämnena med etanol.

Syftet med det här arbetet är att experimentellt studera möjligheten av att förbättra bearbetningen av neemflingor i kolonner genom att utföra lakningen av insektsmedel utan mellanliggande borttagande av det icke-polära lösningsmedlet och att utföra båda lakningssteg samtidigt. Metanol används istället för etanol, eftersom hexan och etanol är lösliga, vilket gör separationen av lösningsmedel efter lakningen svår. Torkningen av resterande lösningsmedel i neemkärnorna är också studerade experimentellt.

Parametrar valda att studera i lakningsdelen är lakningstid, flingtjocklek, volymförhållande av lösningsmedel och total volym lösningsmedel. Alla dessa parametrar visade sig ha stor påverkan på utbytet av insektsmedel, men inverkan av förhållandet av lösningsmedel påverkade mest. Det påvisades att mer metanol än hexan måste användas för att erhålla ett stort utbyte insektsmedel. Utbytet av olja påverkades huvudsakligen av flingtjockleken.

Lakning med den polära- ickepolära lösningsmedelblandningen, jämfört med den sats-visa processen och två-stegsprocessen, resulterade i högre utbyte av insektsmedel på en kortare total processtid, då 2 mm flingtjocklek användes. För den mindre flingtjockleken, 0,7 mm, erhöles 2 procentenheter mindre utbyte av insektsmedel under halva den totala processtiden av två-stegsprocessen.

I torkningsdelen av arbetet är uppenbara slutsatser svåra att göra. Vad som kan sägas är att temperaturen på inkommande luftflöde har inverkan på processen. En högre temperatur resulterar i kortare torktid och högre torkhastighet vid bestämda fukthalter. Slutsatser om torktiden eller torkhastigheten är inte möjliga att göra från resultaten av experimenten. Variationerna i torktider är för stor och torkhastigheten verkar oberoende av tillstånden i tidigare lakningssteg.

Resumen

Este trabajo fue hecho en el departamento de Ingeniería Química del Instituto Real Tecnológico (KTH), de Estocolmo, Suecia. La parte experimental fue realizada en La Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería (UNI), de Managua, Nicaragua. El trabajo es parte de un programa de cooperación entre las dos universidades, financiados por "Swedish International Development Agency" (Asdi). La estadía en Managua fue financiada parcialmente por Asdi a través de una beca "Minor Field Studies".

En Nicaragua, la agricultura contribuye en una proporción importante al producto nacional bruto. Insecticidas sintéticos han sido usados profusamente lo que ha causado efectos negativos en la salud de los seres humanos y la naturaleza. Un insecticida natural puede ser extraído de las semillas de las frutas de un árbol llamado nim que crece en plantaciones en Nicaragua. Las semillas de nim contienen aceite y una mezcla de diferentes sustancias que tienen propiedades insecticidas. El procesamiento de semillas de nim para obtener el insecticida ha sido realizado antes en un proceso por lotes lixiviando semillas molidas de nim en un tanque agitado y en un proceso de dos-pasos lixiviando hojuelas de semilla de nim en columnas. En el primer paso el aceite es lixiviado con hexano y en el segundo paso la mezcla insecticida es lixiviada con etanol.

El objetivo de este trabajo es estudiar experimentalmente la posibilidad de mejorar el procesamiento de las semillas de nim realizando la lixiviación de insecticida sin la remoción intermedia del solvente no polar y realizando los dos pasos de lixiviación simultáneamente. Metanol es usado en lugar de etanol debido a que hexano y etanol son miscibles y esto haría difícil la separación de los solventes después de la lixiviación. El secado de solventes retenidos en las hojuelas de nim también es experimentalmente estudiado.

Los parámetros escogidos para ser estudiados en la parte de lixiviación son: el tiempo de lixiviación, el grosor de las hojuelas, la relación de volúmenes de los solventes y el volumen total de solventes. Todos estos parámetros mostraron tener un gran influencia en el rendimiento de mezcla insecticida, pero es la influencia de la relación de volúmenes de solventes la que tiene mayor importancia. Fue demostrado que tiene que usarse más metanol que hexano para obtener un mayor rendimiento de mezcla insecticida. El rendimiento de aceite es principalmente influenciado por el grosor de la hojuela.

La lixiviación con la mezcla de solventes polar y no polar comparada con el proceso por lotes y el proceso de dos-pasos en columnas, arroja un mayor rendimiento de la mezcla insecticida en menos tiempo usando hojuelas de 2 mm espesor. Para grosores menores (0.7 mm) un rendimiento de 2 unidades menores en % de mezcla insecticida fue obtenido en la mitad del tiempo total en el proceso de dos-pasos.

En la parte de secado del trabajo es difícil sacar conclusiones evidentes. Se puede afirmar que la temperatura del flujo de aire de entrada tiene influencia en el proceso. Una mayor temperatura resulta en un menor tiempo de secado y mayor velocidad de secado a un contenido de humedad dado. Conclusiones sobre el tiempo y la velocidad de secado no son posibles a partir de los resultados experimentales. Las variaciones en los tiempos de secado son demasiado grandes y la velocidad de secado parece ser independiente de las condiciones en los pasos de lixiviación previos.

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1 Introduction

In Nicaragua, agriculture is the main contributor (33 %) to the gross national product (Utrikespolitiska Institutet, 1998). To reduce losses in the production synthetically insecticides have been used extensively. This has provoked negative affects on both human health and the environment. Because of the stability of these compounds they have been accumulating in the soil, plants, animals, water sources and the human body. The insecticides also affect beneficial organisms, such as natural enemies of the target insects. Another problem is the resistance many target insects have gained against these substances over the years (Espinosa, 2000).

1.1 The use of neem seeds

For these reasons it is desirable to find a locally produced, natural biodegradable insecticide with a minimal effect on the environment. Such a product can be derived from the neem tree (*Azadirachta indica A. Juss*), native to the Indian subcontinent.

The neem tree has long been known for its medicinal uses properties and ability to resist plagues and insect attacks. Earliest reference to it is in Sanskrit writings that are over 4,000 years old (Howatt, 1994). All parts of the neem tree, fruits, seeds, oil, bark, leaves, roots and gum, are being used for different purposes. Neem has antiseptic and antibacterial properties, which has provoked the use of neem for various medicinal uses, as example for dental treatments. It is used in many different ways in the regions where it is grown. In India and Africa, the oil and the wood are used as fuel, and in South India the neem tree is a common used furniture wood. The oil that can be extracted from the seed can be used to produce soaps and products for beauty aid (National Research Council, 1992).

The last years the interest in the neem tree has been focused on its insect repellent properties. The neem seed contains oil and a mixture of different substances with insecticide properties. The substance most studied, and which is believed to have the largest contribution to the insect repellence, is Azadirachtin (Aza) (Johansson & Modig, 1996). All parts of the neem tree contain azadirachtin, but the seeds contain the highest concentration. For this reason, in the search for an insecticide, the seeds are the most studied part of the neem tree. Neem is efficient against more than 200 different species of insects. The most common effects of the insecticide are retard growth, inhibit feeding and repellent properties on the species affected (National Research Council, 1992). Studies also indicate that the substance has no effect to humans and other higher organisms, concerning both poisonous and mutagenic aspects. Another advantage is that the natural composition of the neem pesticide, with many different substances working together, makes it unlikely that insects could obtain resistance against it and there are also studies that verify this. The fast biodegradation of the substance is an ecological advantage, but the instability of the obtained products is considered a technical disadvantage (Espinosa, 2000; Johansson & Modig, 1996).

1.2 Characteristics of the neem tree

The neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), member of the Meliaceae family, is a broad leaved, evergreen tree. Nowadays it is also growing in tropical and subtropical parts of Asia, Africa, Australia, Central and South America (Espinosa, 2000; National Research Council, 1992).

It is a fast growing tree: 4-7 meters the first five years, and 5-11 meters during the following five years. It finally reaches a height of 15-20 meters, under favorable conditions up to 35-40 meters (Espinosa, 2000; Wikipedia).

The fruit is a smooth, ellipsoidal drupe, up to about 2 cm long. The tree normally begins bearing fruits after three to five years and becomes fully productive after about ten years, reaching a maximum yield of fruits up to 50 kg seeds/year. It may live for more than two centuries (National Research Council, 1992).

Its root system consists of a strong taproot, which can be twice as long as the total height of the tree. It has well developed lateral roots that efficiently retrieving water and nutrients from the soil. This deep root system is very sensitive to water logging (Howatt, 1994; Wikipedia).

1.3 Chemistry of neem

The active compounds in neem are represented by at least nine groups of triterpenes, or limonoids. New limonoids are still being discovered in neem but azadirachtin, salannin, melantriol, and nimbin are the best known (National Research Council, 1992).

Azadirachtin is the most interesting from an agricultural standpoint because it is relatively abundant in neem seeds and has shown biological activity on a wide range of insects (Howatt, 1994). The molecular formula is $C_{35}H_{44}O_{16}$ and is shown in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Chemistry of azadirachtin

2 Processing of neem

The process of processing the seeds mainly consists of mechanical processing steps. The ripe fruits are pulped and dried, and then stored in sacks during 6 to 8 weeks. After storage, the seeds are husked and fungus contaminated seeds are separated by manual selection. The upper part of figure 2.1 shows a scheme of the process (Espinosa, 2000).

The recovery of insecticide from the neem seeds is performed in two leaching steps, see the lower part of figure 2.1. First, oil is leached with a non-polar solvent, hexane, and then the insecticide is leached with a polar solvent, ethanol. Between the leaching steps and after the recovery of insecticide the solvents must be removed from the exhaust solids. The process may be batch-wise or semi-continuous.

2.1 Processing of the neem seeds to obtain the insecticide

In the batch-wise process ground neem seeds are leached in agitated tanks. Ground seeds are used to obtain a maximal interfacial surface between the solids and the solvents as well as a short diffusion path for the solute since these factors improve the separation. A smaller size of the particles results in a larger interfacial area in the batch. However, the extractors used in the batch-wise process have a great impact on the capital cost. That was demonstrated in the economical study performed by Johansson and Modig (1996). Furthermore, because of the characteristic of the material the most suitable equipment for the removal of solvents after leaching is rather expensive.

In the semi-continuous process neem flakes are used instead of ground seeds. In this case, the leaching steps can be carried out in columns. Not having moving parts, columns are simpler and easier to seal to avoid solvent leakage than agitated tanks. An additional advantage is that owing to the favorable fluid dynamic in a bed consisting of flakes, air is able to flow through the material and the removal of solvents after the leaching steps can be performed in the same equipment.

Several studies have been performed with neem flakes. Martínez et al (1998) studied dissolution kinetic of oil and insecticide in isolated neem seed flakes. Persson and Sjöberg (1998) studied hydrodynamic characteristics and transport parameters in beds consisting of neem seed flakes. Leaching experiments with upward and downward solvent flow in columns packed with neem flakes at different temperatures and flakes thickness were performed by Martínez (2003).

Figure 2.1: Scheme of the neem process

2.2 Improvements of the process

According to the studies mentioned above there are several alternatives to improve the leaching process that deserve attention:

The possibility of replacing both solvents by using only water to perform the leaching is one alternative. One of the problems of water leaching is the instability of the insecticide in water solutions. Kleeberg (1997) reported a successfully process where azadirachtin, the active insecticide compound, is leached from the seeds with water in a first step and then transferred to another stabilizing solvent by liquid-liquid extraction. Even though another solvent and further separation steps are introduced in the processes there is a potential to improve the manufacturing process with investigations in that direction.

To carry out the second leaching step without the intermediate removal of the non-polar solvent, and by perform simultaneously both leaching steps is another alternative. Using two immiscible solvents one could perform this. Oil is removed in a first step because of its own value and the fact that its presence in the flakes prevents the insecticide to be leached by the polar solvent. With a mobile immiscible liquid mixture in contact with the solids, both leaching steps would occur simultaneously in the sites occupied by the two liquid phases. The solvents remaining in the material could be removed directly in the column by drying it with hot air. The solvents could then be recovered from the air by condensation. In this alternative, the number of separation steps is not reduced since a leaching step is replaced by the separation of two liquid phases. However, both separations will occurs simultaneously and the total operation time will be reduced.

3 Objectives

The purpose of this work is to experimentally study the feasibility of improving the processing of neem flakes in columns by performing the leaching of insecticide without intermediate removal of the non-polar solvent and by performing simultaneously both leaching steps. These experiments will be performed using hexane and methanol as solvents. By study how different variables affects the yield of insecticide compounds and oil, and compare the yield with earlier studies, it is possible to evaluate if this method is suitable.

The drying of the solvents remaining in the neem flakes will also be experimentally studied. This will be performed in the same column as the leaching takes place. The weight of the flakes and solvents will be measured during the whole experiment, to be able to get information of drying time and drying rate. The out coming gas composition will also be measured to analyze the composition of hexane and methanol as the drying proceeds.

4 Theory

This chapter concerns general theory of leaching and drying as well as different mechanisms that occurs depending on which steps are controlling the processes.

4.1 Solid-liquid extraction/ Leaching

Solid-liquid extraction, or leaching, generally refers to the removal of a substance, or substances, from a solid via a liquid extraction media, a solvent. If the solute is uniformly dispersed in the solid, the material close to the surface will first be dissolved, leaving a porous structure in the solid residue. The solvent will then have to penetrate this outer layer before it can reach further solute, and the process will become progressively more difficult and the extraction rate will fall. Generally the process can be considered in three parts: first the change of phase of the solute as it dissolves in the solvent, secondly its diffusion through the solvent in the pores of the solvent to the outside of the particle, and thirdly the transfer of the solute from the solution in contact with the particles to the main bulk of the solution. Any of these three processes may be responsible for limiting the extraction rate, though the first process usually occurs so rapidly that it has negligible effect on the overall rate (Coulson and Richardson, 2002).

4.1.1 Factors influencing the rate of extraction

There are different ways to describe the mechanisms depending of which step is controlling the process. If the controlling factor is the diffusion of the solute through the porous structure of the residual solids, the material should be of small size so that the distance the solute has to travel is small. Further, if the controlling factor is the diffusion of the solute from the surface of the particle to the bulk of the solution, a high degree of agitation is required.

There are four important factors that aid in leaching:

Particle size. The smaller the particle size, the greater is the interfacial area between the solid and liquid and therefore the higher is the rate of transfer of material. Furthermore, the smaller is the distance the solute must diffuse within the solid. On the other hand, the surface may not be so effectively used with a very fine material if circulation of the liquid is impeded, and separation of the particles from the liquid and the drainage of the solid residue are made more difficult. It is generally desirable that the range of particle size should be small so that each particle requires approximately the same time for extraction and, in particular, the production of a large amount of fine material should be avoided as it may wedge in the interstices of the large particles and impede the flow of the solvent.

Solvent. The liquid chosen should be a good selective solvent and its viscosity should be sufficiently low for it to circulate freely. Generally, a relatively pure solvent will be used

initially, but as the extraction proceeds the concentration of solute will increase and the rate of extraction will progressively decrease, first because the concentration gradient will be reduced and secondly because the solution will generally become more viscous. Furthermore, the solvent selection plays an important role in the separation steps that follow leaching.

Temperature. Temperature is adjusted to optimize solubility and mass transfer. In most cases, the solubility of the material that is being extracted will increase with temperature to give a higher rate of extraction. Further the diffusion coefficient will be expected to increase with rise in temperature and this will also improve the rate. In some cases, the upper limit of temperature is determined by secondary considerations, such as the material properties.

Agitation of the fluid. Agitation of the solvent is important because it increases the eddy diffusion and therefore increases the transfer of material from the surface of the particle to the bulk of the solution. Further, agitation of suspensions of fine particles prevents sedimentation and more effective use is made of the interfacial surface (Coulson and Richardson, 2002). Since the leaching is performed in a column agitation of the fluid is not possible to achieve.

4.2 Drying

The process of drying a porous solid consists of simultaneous heat and mass transfer. Drying by convection is governed by external transfer, phase equilibria and internal transfer. Different mechanisms and controlling steps determine the total process. The external transfer is the convective heat and mass transfer in the gas phase, and the internal transfer are the transport mechanisms existing in transport through the capillaries. The internal transfer is very difficult to elucidate due to the complex solid structure and different mechanisms for heat and mass transfer involved in the process.

In drying of a single component, only the rate of evaporation of that single component is of interest. In multicomponent drying the composition of solvents is also important to consider, since a drying process is normally not run to completion and the remaining moisture considerably affects product quality.

In drying in columns heated air passes continuously up through a stationary permeable bed of wet material, and is removed from the top of the column. Through-circulation dryers are restricted in application granular materials that permit free flow-circulation of air. Many materials meet this requirement without special preparation. Others require pretreatment to render them suitable for through circulation drying. The process of converting a wet solid into a form suitable for through circulation of air is called performing. Drying times are usually much shorter than in parallel-flow tray dryers. Drying rates are high because of the large contact area and short distance of travel for the

internal moisture. As the drying proceeds the drying rate becomes lower, since the internal moisture becomes progressively harder to remove from the material (Perry, 1997).

4.2.1 External transfer

The transfer of vapours from the liquid surface to the gas stream has a significant influence of the overall rate of evaporation and on the process controlling step. Stringent external conditions may cause control by internal transfer, less intensive external conditions may cause control by phase equilibria or external transfer. Drying rates are usually described in terms of heat and mass transfer coefficients and driving forces. The transfer coefficients mainly depend on the flowing conditions, the contact mode between the phases and the physical properties of the flowing media. Temperatures and concentration differences constitute the driving forces for heat and mass transfer. The convective evaporation occurs in a layer near the interface where the temperature and concentration vary continuously until the bulk conditions are reached, see figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Convective evaporation from a flake into a gas stream.

4.2.2 Internal transfer

The main mechanisms involved in the internal mass transfer during drying of a porous solid containing a multicomponent mixture are summarized as follows:

- Liquid flow due to capillary forces
- Flow by gravitational force
- Liquid and gas flow due to total pressure gradients
- Surface diffusion
- Moisture migration due to thermal gradients
- Diffusion in liquid phase
- Diffusion in gas phase

These mechanisms of internal heat and mass transfer involve driving forces, which allow mass and energy to flow in the porous material. The fluxes are usually expressed as functions of transport parameters and driving forces.

Liquid and gas flow due to total pressure gradients are only taken into consideration when the porous solid undergoes pressure differences. Surface diffusion occurs when active surfaces undergo adsorption. These mechanisms can be disregarded in the case of this thesis. During drying of a porous solid containing a single solvent, mass transfer consists of the movement of liquid due to capillary and gravitational forces as well as diffusion of vapours in the porous space not occupied by the liquid phase. Liquid content and concentration gradients result from temperature gradients. If the process is isothermal there are no temperature gradients, and heat flux and concentration gradients are not possible either the liquid consist of a single component.

If the liquid consists of a multicomponent liquid mixture, diffusion takes place even under isothermal conditions during drying of a porous solid. Furthermore, molecular diffusion in liquid phase is superimposed to the capillary movement of the liquid mixture. Usually, when solvents evaporate at the surface, concentration gradients are created in the liquid. That induces concentration gradients in the interstitial gas, which is in equilibrium with the liquid. The contribution of diffusion in gas phase to mass transfer increases as the drying progresses since the space available for the gas increases. Diffusion in multicomponent gas and liquid mixtures is interactive and constitutes together with the capillary movement of the liquid one of the main mechanisms for mass transfer during isothermal drying of a porous solid containing a multicomponent liquid mixture.

5 Mathematical model of the drying

A bed consisting of wet porous flakes is going to be dried by passing hot air through the bed. The mathematical model to describe the heat and mass transfer, between and within the flakes, during drying of the bed is very complex. For this reason some simplifications of the model are required. Simplifying the model from a bed containing a porous solid, to consider the solid as separate flakes, performs this. A schematic figure of the packed bed and the flakes are shown in figure 5.1.

Changes in the gas phase are considered when it passes through the bed. Here theory for a gas flow through a porous bed is applied (dispersion, advection equation and energy balance). These changes are connected to changes in the flakes, where theory for liquid and heat in the separate flakes is applied. The simultaneous solution of these mass and energy balances is connected by concentration and liquid content in the flakes and in the bed. Boundary conditions relate mass and heat fluxes between the gas and the flakes.

Figure 5.1: Schematic figure of the packed bed and the flakes.

5.1 Assumptions

Assumptions made to simplify the actual situation are:

- The main changes of the gas phase occur in axial direction, and radial changes are neglected.
- It is assumed that most of the liquid is occupying the porosity inside the flakes, and liquid between the flakes is neglected. The flakes have, at the beginning, a thin liquid film and air can easily pass between them.
- The flakes are regarded as finite slabs of uniform size.
- The thickness of the flakes is small compared to the other dimensions, and the transfer area of the edges is therefore neglected.
- Heat and mass transfer in the flakes are one-dimensional, in the direction of the thickness.
- It is assumed that there is no evaporation inside the flakes and the drying will occur only by convective evaporation from a plane surface to the gas stream.
- Transport coefficients are independent of temperature and liquid content.

5.2 Mass balances

5.2.1 Mass transfer in the gas phase

If the gas velocity, v , is assumed to be constant the axial changes of solvent vapour concentration in the gas are described by the dispersion advection equation:

$$\frac{\partial C_g}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C_g}{\partial z^2} - v \frac{\partial C_g}{\partial z} + R_i \quad (5.1)$$

where C_g is the concentration of solvent vapour in the gas phase per total volume, D is the dispersion coefficient, t is the time, z the bed height, v the gas velocity and R_i the solvent vapour added to the gas stream due to the evaporation from the surface of the flakes per volume bed. This production term is assumed to be homogeneous and is justified if the flakes are small compared to the diameter of the bed.

5.2.2 Mass transfer in the flakes

The equation of the mass transfer within the flakes is similar to that of the whole bed. Since the particle in question is in a certain location z , and the particles have the shape of slabs, the derivative of moisture content will be with respect to the particle thickness, x , instead of the bed height z , see figure 5.1.

$$\frac{\partial u_p}{\partial t} = D_L \frac{\partial^2 u_p}{\partial x^2} \quad (5.2)$$

where u_p is the liquid volume per particle volume and D_L is the liquid diffusivity in the flakes.

5.2.3 Coupling between the phases

The solvent vapour added to the gas stream due to the evaporation from the surface of the flakes can be expressed as:

$$R_i = -(1 - \varepsilon) \cdot a_p \cdot c_l \cdot D_L \frac{\partial u_p}{\partial x} \quad (5.3)$$

where ε is the porosity, a_p the specific area of the flake, c_l the total concentration of the liquid phase.

5.3 Energy balances

5.3.1 Heat transfer in the gas phase

The heat transfer in the gas phase may be determined by performing an energy balance:

$$\frac{\partial T_g}{\partial t} = D_{H,g} \frac{\partial^2 T_g}{\partial z^2} - \frac{v}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial T_g}{\partial z} + \frac{Q_i}{\rho c_p} \quad (5.4)$$

where T_g is the temperature of the gas, $D_{H,g}$ the heat diffusivity of the gas, ρ the density of the solvent, c_p the specific heat, and Q_i the energy of the solvent vapour added to the gas stream.

$$Q_i = (1 - \varepsilon) a_p [-h(T_g - T_p) + R_i \lambda M_w] \quad (5.5)$$

5.3.2 Heat transfer in the flakes

Analogously the heat transfer in the flakes is:

$$\frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = D_{H,p} \frac{\partial^2 T_p}{\partial x^2} \quad (5.6)$$

where T_p is the temperature of the flakes and $D_{H,p}$ is the heat diffusivity of the flakes.

5.4 Initial and boundary conditions

5.4.1 Initial conditions

In the bed

$$C_g = C_{g,0} \quad 0 \leq z \leq H \quad t = 0 \quad (5.7)$$

$$T_g = T_{g,0} \quad 0 \leq z \leq H \quad t = 0 \quad (5.8)$$

In the flakes

$$u_p = u_{p,0} \quad -L/2 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad t = 0 \quad (5.9)$$

$$T_p = T_{p,0} \quad -L/2 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad t = 0 \quad (5.10)$$

5.4.2 Boundary conditions

In the bed

$$-D \frac{\partial C_g}{\partial z} + vC_g = vC_{g,in} \quad z = 0 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.11)$$

$$-D_{H,g} \frac{\partial T_g}{\partial z} + vT_g = vT_{g,in} \quad z = 0 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_g}{\partial z} = 0 \quad z = H \quad t > 0 \quad (5.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_g}{\partial z} = 0 \quad z = H \quad t > 0 \quad (5.14)$$

In the flakes

$$\frac{\partial u_p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad x = 0 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.15)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad x = 0 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.16)$$

$$-c_l D_L \left. \frac{\partial u_p}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L/2} = N_w \quad x = L/2 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.17)$$

$$-k \left. \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L/2} = h(T_g - T_p) - N_w \lambda M_w \quad x = L/2 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.18)$$

$$\text{with } N_w = h_D \frac{C_T}{C_{Bm}} (C_{g,s} - C_{g,b}) \quad x = L/2 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.19)$$

$$\text{and } C_{g,s} = \frac{P_w(T_p)}{RT_p} \quad x = L/2 \quad t > 0 \quad (5.20)$$

Equations for a numerical solution are shown in appendix A.

6 Experimental part

To experimentally study the leaching of insecticide without intermediate removal of the non-polar solvent will permit to examine how the leaching of insecticide with methanol is affected by the presence of the non-polar solvent, hexane. The matter of concern when both leaching steps are performed simultaneously is the yield of insecticide compared to the two-steps process. Another matter of interest is the separation of the liquid phases after the leaching.

As a first step the experimental work was aimed at determining if the process improvements mentioned in the latter part of chapter 2.2 are feasible and to search suitable conditions for the leaching of insecticide without intermediate drying of the non-polar solvent and to perform the two leaching steps in a single step.

The laboratory experiments were also aimed at elucidating mechanisms, to determine specific data and to determine the influence of the process variables on the leaching process and the removal of solvents from the bed of flakes.

The drying of the exhaust flakes was studied to see if it is possible to dry the remaining solvents successfully in the column. Since if the remaining solvents are removed in the same column as the leaching is performed in, experimental data useful for the whole process can be obtained from single experiments.

6.1 Material

The neem seeds used in the experiments came from COPYNIM, a company manufacturing neem products, located outside Managua. At COPYNIM's factory the neem seeds were husked and selected. At UNI the seeds were then made into flakes, using a mill.

Thicknesses of 0.7, 1.3 and 2 mm have been studied before by Persson and Sjöberg (1998) and Martínez (2003). In these studies, it has been shown that these thicknesses are suitable for both the leaching and the drying experiments. In addition they are easy to produce in the existing equipment. However, only thicknesses of 0.7 mm and 2 mm were used in this study because of shortage of time.

Commercial hexane was used to leach the oil and methanol (99.8 %) was used to leach the insecticide compounds.

6.2 Equipment

The intension was to perform both the leaching and the drying in the same column, but with the existing equipment this was not possible. The leaching of the seeds was performed in a soxhlet, and then the wetted seeds were moved to a column to be dried. A more detailed description of the equipment is given in the following subchapters.

6.2.1 Leaching

The leaching was performed in a soxhlet connected to a condenser and a round-bottom flask (500 ml). The condensing water held a temperature of 16°C, regulated with a thermal bath. A heating mantle was used to heat the solvents.

Figure 6.1: Experimental set-up of the leaching equipment.

6.2.2 Drying

To perform the drying of the exhaust flakes, they were placed in a column made of PVC, with an inner diameter of 55 mm and a height of 180 mm. In the bottom of the column a net was placed to hold the flakes in the bed. To this column air of controlled conditions were introduced at the bottom.

Air taken from atmosphere by a blower was conducted through an adsorption column that reduced its humidity, and then it was heated passing through a tube section with an electrical resistance. The hot and dry air stream flowed through the column and dried the flakes. The airflow from the blower was regulated with a frequency inverter connected to a power supply.

A sample from the outflow was with regular time intervals taken through a spectrophotometer to analyze the composition of hexane and methanol during the whole drying experiment.

The gas temperature was controlled by an automatic control loop that regulated the energy supply to the electrical resistance. The inlet and the outlet temperatures of the column were measured using thermocouples connected to a computer.

Figure 6.2: Experimental set-up of the drying equipment.

6.3 Procedure

In the experiments different variables were studied to evaluate their effect on the leaching and drying processes. The variables were thickness of the flakes, volume ratio of the solvents, total volume of solvents, leaching time and drying temperature. In every experiment 70 grams of neem flakes were used.

6.3.1 Leaching

The net containing the flakes were placed in the soxhlet and the solvents in the round-bottom flask. The solvents, heated from the heating mantle, evaporated up into the condenser, where it condensed. The bottom of the soxhlet captured the condensed solvents, until the liquid level in the soxhlet passed the top of the smaller external pipe. Then the solvents fell back into the flask by capillary force. This continued for 10, 20 or 30 hours.

6.3.2 Drying

During the drying experiment the mass of the wet flakes was measured using an analytical balance. In the beginning the weight was determined every minute, and when the experiment proceeded and the changes in mass were smaller, every five to ten minutes. By monitoring gas composition from the out flow using a spectrophotometer, the fraction of the two solvents could be evaluated. This information makes it possible to see how the solvents are dried individually.

6.4 *Experimental evaluation*

Yield of oil and insecticide compounds

Immediately after the drying was ended the weight of the flakes were measured, totally dried in an oven, and then measured again. The last measurement corresponded to the dried solid and by using the difference of the two measurements the moisture content of the flakes after the drying could be evaluated.

To determine the yield of oil and insecticide compounds, the two-phase mixture from the leaching, hexane containing oil and methanol containing insecticide compounds, were separated. This was performed using a separation funnel. Hexane was then evaporated in a rotary evaporator and the oil residue weighed. The weight of insecticide compounds was calculated using a mass balance according to:

$$m_{\text{insecticide}} = m_{s,0} - m_s - m_{\text{oil}}$$

where $m_{s,0}$ is the initial weight of the flakes, m_s is the weight of the dried flakes and m_{oil} is the weight of the oil.

Drying rate

The drying rate was calculated according to:
$$N = -m_s \frac{du}{dt \cdot A}$$

where N is the molar flux, u is the moisture content, t the time and A the specific area. Values of the drying rate are shown in appendix B, and diagrams of drying rate vs. moisture content are shown in appendix C.

Concentration of out coming solvent

The results from the spectrophotometer have to be transformed from volume to concentration according to:

$$C_A = V_A \cdot \frac{\rho_A}{M_A} \cdot \frac{1}{V_{\text{cell}}}$$

where C_A is the concentration of A, ρ_A is the density of A, M_A is the molar weight of A, V_A is the total volume of A, measured by the spectrophotometer, and V_{cell} is the cell volume.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{MeOH}} &= 792 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} & \rho_{\text{Hex}} &= 659 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \\ M_{\text{MeOH}} &= 32.04 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kmol}} & M_{\text{Hex}} &= 86.17 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kmol}} & V_{\text{cell}} &= 0.5 \text{ L} \end{aligned}$$

Values of the volume and the concentration of hexane and methanol are shown in appendix E, together with diagrams of the concentration of each solvent vs. time. Data of densities and molar weights was taken from Perry (1997).

7 Results and Discussion

This chapter of the thesis consists of two subchapters. The first one concerns the simultaneous leaching process and considers the evaluation of the yields of oil and insecticide compounds, including comparisons with earlier studies. The second one concerns the drying process.

7.1 Leaching experiments and yield of oil and insecticide

The purpose in this section is to evaluate what influence different parameters have on the leaching, so that suitable conditions for the leaching can be evaluated. In the first subsection the chosen parameters are considered and in the second other parameters affecting the results are taken into account.

7.1.1 Influence of operation parameters

The tested conditions of the experiments are listed in the table 7.1. Leaching time, thickness of the flakes and volume ratio of solvents were the studied parameters. During the leaching experiments it was shown that the total volume of solvents also affects, while it also became a parameter to discuss.

Leaching time (hours)	Flake thickness (mm)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)
10	2	1:1	300
10	2	1:2	300
10	2	2:1	300
20	2	1:1	300
20	2	1:2	300
20	2	1:2	450
20	2	3:4	350
20	2	1:3	400
30	2	1:2	450
30	2	1:3	400
20	0.7	1:2	300
20	0.7	1:3	400

Table 7.1: Summary of the tested conditions for leaching.

Influence of the leaching time

Martínez (2003), studied leaching kinetics in columns for the oil and the insecticide compounds from neem. In that study it was shown that oil is being leached much faster than the insecticide compounds. The results from this study, shown in table 7.2 and 7.3 agree with the results from that study. The leaching was performed during 10, 20 and 30 hours. According to the results, the higher leaching time, the higher yield of insecticide compounds is reached. The yield of oil reaches about the same value independent of the leaching time. Oil is leached much faster than the insecticide compounds. This indicates that equilibrium is reached earlier with oil than with insecticide compounds.

Leaching time (hours)	Flake thickness (mm)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
10	2	1:2	300	35.8	35.8	7.4	7.4
20	2	1:2	300	35.5 35.3	35.4	10.3 11.0	10.65

Table 7.2: Influence of the leaching time.

Leaching time (hours)	Flake thickness (mm)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
20	2	1:3	400	33.9 33.6	33.75	13.1 13.5	13.3
30	2	1:3	400	34.4 34.0 33.8 34.4	34.15	19.3 18.8 18.1 18.0	18.55

Table 7.3: Influence of the leaching time.

Influence of the thickness of the flakes

When using flakes of thickness 0.7 mm, the yield of oil is remarkably larger than when using a thickness of 2 mm. The yield of insecticide is also greater, but not as much as the yield of oil, see table 7.4 and 7.5. When the flakes are thinner, the specific area is greater, which allows the solvents to leach more oil and insecticide. The diffusion path is also shorter which results in faster mass transfer.

Flake thickness (mm)	Leaching time (hours)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
0.7	20	1:2	300	42.9 40.0 47.0	43.3	14.1 18.4 9.4	13.97
2	20	1:2	300	35.5 35.3	35.4	10.3 11.0	10.65

Table 7.4: Influence of the thickness of the flakes.

Flake thickness (mm)	Leaching time (hours)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
0.7	20	1:3	400	40.9 43.4	42.15	15.5 12.6	14.05
2	20	1:3	400	33.9 33.6	37.5	13.1 13.5	13.3

Table 7.5: Influence of the thickness of the flakes.

The results when using a thickness of the flakes of 0.7 mm are rather uncertain, because a white wax appears directly after the leaching. What the wax consists of is not known. Probably it is pure oil, but it could also be some kind of mixture of oil and the two solvents. This makes the different compounds in the mixture (hexane, methanol, oil, insecticide and wax) hard to separate. Because of the difficult separation the results are very insecure, which can be seen in the considerable variation in the oil and insecticide yields in the experiments where 0.7 mm thickness where used (see tables above).

Influence of the ratio and volume of solvents

Table 7.6 shows that using different ratios of hexane and methanol have a significant influence of the yield of insecticide compounds, while the yield of oil only vary slightly. The highest yield of insecticide compounds is reached when more methanol than hexane is used.

The yield of oil is approximately the same independent of both ratio and volume of solvents. An exception is when equal volumes of the two solvents, or more hexane than methanol is being used, but in those cases the yield of insecticide compounds are too low to use, see table 7.7. The yield of insecticide compounds is influenced though. When 100 ml of hexane is used, the yield of insecticide compounds is higher than with 150 ml hexane, and when using a larger total volume of solvents, the yield of insecticide compounds decreases, (compare the two experiments with ratio 1 to 2 when the flakes have been leached for 20 hours, table 7.7).

Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Flake thickness (mm)	Leaching time (hours)	Oil (%)	Insecticide (%)
2:1	300	2	10	39.0	1.8
1:1	300	2	10	38.1	2.8
1:2	300	2	10	35.8	7.4

Table 7.6: Influence of the solvent ratio.

It seems like adsorption preferably occurs with hexane rather than methanol. Probably, when using a larger volume of solvents, hexane is occupying the space where methanol is

supposed to leach the insecticide compounds, which results in less insecticide compounds even though more methanol is in the system.

So far it has been shown that both the ratio and the volume of solvents affect the yield of oil and insecticide compounds. When analyzing the table below it can be realized that comparing the same volume with different ratios gives a large difference in both the yield of oil and insecticide compounds, while comparing the same ratio with different volumes only gives a small difference of the total effect. According to these results the parameter affecting most of the two is the ratio between the solvents, but the influence of the volume is definitely not negligible. To be sure of how the ratio and the volume of solvents effects the yield of oil and insecticide compounds, more studies are recommended.

Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Leaching time (hours)	Flake thickness (mm)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
1:1	300	20	2	40.6	40.6	5.5	5.5
1:2	300	20	2	35.5 35.3	35.4	10.3 11.0	10.65
1:2	450	20	2	35.5	35.5	8.6	8.6
3:4	350	20	2	37.0	37.0	7.1	7.1
1:3	400	20	2	33.9 33.6	33.75	13.1 13.5	13.3
1:2	450	30	2	36.3	36.3	9.9	9.9
1:3	400	30	2	34.4 34.0 33.8 34.4	34.15	19.3 18.8 18.1 18.0	18.55

Table 7.7: Influence of the ratio and volume of solvents.

7.1.2 Influence of other parameters

Not only parameters chosen to be studied affect the results of the leaching. Other parameters that are difficult, and sometimes impossible to influence, can make a significant difference in the leaching process.

Influence of material

All results from similar experiments shows a variation in yields of oil and insecticide, see chapter 7.1.3, table 7.8. A small variation is natural, since the oil and insecticide compounds content in the seeds varies some from tree to tree, and thereby seed to seed. When larger differences appear, natural variation is not the cause.

Losses of oil

Oil is lost when the seeds are made into flakes in the mill, and probably some insecticide compounds are also lost here. This loss is not of great importance though, since it occurs before the initial weight of the seeds, and before they are getting leached and therefore not affects the result. Person and Sjöberg, 1998, studied the weight loss at flake production. The results showed that almost 8 percent of the initial weight was lost in the production of flakes with thickness of 0.7 mm, and almost 2 percent of flakes with thickness of 2 mm.

The losses that are of importance concerning the reliability of the results are the losses that occur after the leaching begins. Oil is lost on the walls of the round bottom flask when the mixture of hexane, methanol, oil and insecticide compounds is moved to the separator. And some oil is lost in the feeding of the solution with oil and hexane, to the evaporator. These losses directly affect the determination of yield of insecticide compounds.

The weight of the insecticide compounds is calculated based on the weight of the oil (see chapter 6.4), which means that if the losses of oil are large, the calculated yield of the insecticide is also affected. To see if the losses of oil are important, the solution of methanol and insecticide compounds was evaporated. The results showed that the losses of oil are negligible when calculating the yield of insecticide.

7.1.3 Summary of the leaching results in numbers

Leaching time (hours)	Flake thickness (mm)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Oil (%)	Average (%)	Insecticide (%)	Average (%)
10	2	1:1	300	38.1	38.1	2.8	2.8
10	2	1:2	300	35.8	35.8	7.4	7.4
10	2	2:1	300	39.0	39.0	1.8	1.8
20	2	1:1	300	40.6	40.6	5.5	5.5
20	2	1:2	300	35.5 35.3	35.4	10.3 11.0	10.65
20	2	1:2	450	35.5	35.5	8.6	8.6
20	2	3:4	350	37.0	37.0	7.1	7.1
20	2	1:3	400	33.9 33.6	33.75	13.1 13.5	13.3
30	2	1:2	450	36.3	36.3	9.9	9.9
30	2	1:3	400	34.4 34.0 33.8 34.4	34.15	19.3 18.8 18.1 18.0	18.55
20	0.7	1:2	300	42.9 40.0 47.0	43.3	14.1 18.4 9.4	13.97
20	0.7	1:3	400	40.9 43.4	42.15	15.5 12.6	14.05

Table 7.8: Summary of results.

7.1.4 Comparison of the leaching results with earlier studies

Espinosa (2000) leached ground neem seeds in a multistage counter-current batch extractor. The seeds were first leached with hexane to extract the oil, and then with ethanol to extract the insecticide compounds (see also chapter 2.1). The results are shown in table 7.8. Martínez (2003) used neem flakes of different thicknesses in a two-step process leached in columns. First the flakes were leached for 20 hours with hexane, to leach the oil, and then they were dried. After that they were leached for 20 hours with ethanol, to leach the insecticide compounds, and at last dried again. See results in table 7.9.

The conditions resulting in the largest yield of insecticide compounds in this study, when simultaneous leaching was used, were when the flakes were leached for 30 hours, the flake thickness was 2 mm and the ratio of hexane and methanol was 1 to 3. See table 7.8. If the 0.7 mm flakes had been leached for 30 hours, it probably would have resulted in an even higher, or at least the same, yield of insecticide as when the 2 mm flakes were leached for 30 hours.

Comparing the yields of both oil and insecticide compounds from this study with the batch-wise process, shows that both yields are higher when using simultaneous leaching. When comparing the results with the two-step process it can be realized that for the 2 mm flakes, the yield of insecticide compounds is much larger in the simultaneous leaching and the yield of oil is less. For the 0.7 mm flakes the yield of oil is comparable, but the yield of insecticide compounds is less.

Because hexane and ethanol are miscible it was not possible to use these two solvents in simultaneous leaching, since the separation afterwards would have been to complicate. For this reason methanol, which has similar properties as ethanol, was used instead. Hexane and methanol are completely immiscible. Which of the solvents, ethanol or methanol, that has the largest capacity to leach insecticide compounds, is not known. Separate studies to evaluate solvent properties must be performed for that knowledge.

Different leaching procedures and solvents combinations make the results complicated to compare. It is not possible to tell whether it is the way of leaching, or the change of solvent, that affect the yields most.

When using a mixture of hexane and methanol in simultaneous leaching results in a higher yield of insecticide compounds for 2 mm flakes, than using hexane and ethanol one by one in the two-step process. For 0.7 mm flakes the yield of insecticide is higher in the two-step process. The yield of oil is larger in the two-step process when using flakes of thickness 2 mm, and about the same using 0.7 mm thickness.

Until now, the total process time has not been considered. The simultaneous leaching, compared to the two-step process, reduces a leaching and a drying step, and instead a separation step is added. Using 2 mm flakes, in simultaneous leaching, the yield of

insecticide compounds is larger than in the two-step process when the flakes were leached 20 hours, and nearly twice as much when the flakes were leached 30 hours (see table 7.8 and 7.10). By using simultaneous leaching the total process time is reduced, and the yield of insecticide is higher. Using 0.7 mm flakes, the yield of insecticide is still higher in the two-step process than in the simultaneous leaching. But the flakes were only leached for 20 hours. If they were leached 30 hours the yield of insecticide would most certainly be a lot higher than in the two-step process, and the total process time would be reduced.

	Oil (%)	Insecticide (%)
Ground neem seeds	32.4	11.4

Table 7.9: Results from Espinosa (2000).

Flake thickness (mm)	Leaching time (hours)	Oil (%)	Insecticide (%)
2	2*20	41.40	10.37
0.7	2*20	43.26	16.73

Table 7.10: Results from Martínez (2003).

7.2 Drying

The purpose in this section is to evaluate what influence different parameters have on the drying on flakes after extraction, so that suitable conditions for the drying can be evaluated.

7.2.1 Influence of parameters

The flakes used in the drying experiments are the same flakes that were leached, and therefore the properties of the material in the drying were the same as for the leaching, see chapter 7.1.1, table 7.1. The only additional parameter was the drying gas temperature. In all experiments the gas temperature was 40 degrees, except one, where the gas temperature was 60 degrees.

Influence of the temperature during drying

As expected, the drying time is reduced when the gas temperature increases. See diagram 7.1.

Diagram 7.1: Influence of the drying temperature.

Diagram 7.2 shows drying curves at both temperatures. No constant drying period exists, but only a falling drying period. A constant drying period would indicate that external heat and mass transfer are limiting the process. The drying curve shows that a faster drying rate occurs at certain moisture content using the higher temperature, than when using the lower temperature. Using a higher temperature makes the gas more difficult to saturate, which makes it possible to dry the flakes faster. The drying curves for all other experiments look the same and are shown in appendix C together with the moisture content vs. time curves. These results are not possible to compare with the general theory of convection drying, since the air does not have an uniform temperature or moisture content in the bed.

Diagram 7.2: Influence of the drying temperature.

Moisture content

The moisture content in the beginning of the drying is higher when the smaller thickness is used. The larger thickness has moisture content of approximately 1.1-1.3 g solvent/g dry seeds when the flakes were leached for 20 hours, and 1.2-1.7 g solvent/g dry seeds when leached for 30 hours. The moisture content when using the smaller thickness was 1.8-2 g solvent/g dry seeds when leached 20 hours, see table 7.13.

Probably, the interaction between the flakes and the liquid is larger with a larger specific area. More oil and insecticide compounds, both in fraction and in absolute terms, were leached when using 0.7 mm flakes than when using 2 mm flakes, according to the results shown in chapter 7.1, table 7.8. Also, it seems like a connection between the moisture content in the beginning of the drying and the yields of extracted oil and insecticide compounds is possible to make. The more oil and insecticide compounds leached the higher moisture content of the flakes at the beginning of the drying.

After the drying in the column the flakes were placed in the oven to dry the last remaining moisture. The moisture content in the flakes, after the drying in column, varied both for different experiments and for experiments performed under the same conditions. See table 7.11.

The differences may be due to that the incoming air has not the same moisture content in all experiments. The moisture content left in the seeds after the drying partly depends of the humidity of the incoming air to the column. Drying of the flakes take place until equilibrium between the air and the flakes appears. Beyond this stage no driving force exists to further dry the flakes. A more humidified incoming air flow results in that equilibrium occurs with a higher concentration of solvents left in the flakes. With a less humidified incoming air flow this equilibrium takes place at a lower liquid content and at a later stage, which allows the flakes to be drier in the end.

The remaining moisture content also depend on how the bed is packed, e g how much of the pores that are blocked by other flakes. When the pores are blocked, the air stream cannot reach the solvents. The bed is never packed in the exact same way, which means that different amounts of solvents are unreachable for the air stream. In the oven, where the mass transfer area is changed, the flakes are getting totally dried.

Flake thickness (mm)	Leaching time (hours)	Volume ratio of solvents (hexane:meOH)	Total volume of solvents (ml)	Moisture content at the beginning of the drying (g solvent/g dry solid)	Moisture content at the end of the drying (g solvent/g dry solid)	Dried moisture (g solvent/g dry solid)
2	10	1:1	300	1.06	-	1.06 ¹
				1.09	-	1.09 ¹
2	10	1:2	300	0.93	-	0.93 ¹
				0.99	-	0.99 ¹
2	20	1:1	300	1.30	0.07	1.23
2	20	1:2	300	1.28	0.05	1.24
				1.19	0.09	1.11
2	20	1:2	450	1.13	0.05	1.08
2	20	1:3	400	1.29	0.09	1.19
				1.35	0.09	1.25
2	30	1:2	450	1.28	0.07	1.17
2	30	1:3	400	1.66	0.21	1.46
				1.62	0.18	1.44
				1.53	0.18	1.35
				1.43	0.10	1.33
0.7	20	1:2	300	2.01	0.11	1.90
				1.90	0.09	1.81
0.7	20	1:3	400	1.93	0.09	1.85
				1.85	0.04	1.81

Table 7.11: Moisture content at the beginning and at the end of drying.

¹ The seeds were not placed in the oven after drying, while these values are too high.

Influence of the leaching time on drying

The longer time the seeds are being leached, the more porous the material becomes. A more porous material means a longer diffusion path, but also that liquid can be transported more easily. These two phenomena counteract each other. Which one of them affects most was supposed to be evaluated by comparing experiments leached under the same conditions except for the hours of leaching. Unfortunately, comparison between the different leaching times is impossible, because the drying time in similar experiments

vary too much, see moisture content versus time curves in appendix C. The variations in drying time are discussed in the section below.

Variation in drying time

In the beginning the moisture has a short diffusion path to reach the bulk, and moisture content decreases very fast with time. As the drying proceeds the diffusion path becomes longer and the drying of the last remaining moisture is slow (see appendix C). These results agree with theory. For repeated experiments a considerable variation in drying time was observed though. For example, in the experiment repeated four times, with flakes of thickness 2 mm leached during 30 hours and using a hexane and methanol ratio of three to one, completely different times were required to reach the same liquid content, (see diagram 7.3). To dry the seeds until 0.4 g solvent/ g dry solid remains takes about the same time in all experiments. However, after that the curves take different shapes. In two of the experiments the moisture content continues to decrease rapidly, while in the other two the changes in moisture content with time are very small. These variations make conclusions concerning the drying time difficult to make.

Diagram 7.3: Variations in drying time.

The moisture content of the flakes at the beginning of the drying affects the drying time, but this is almost certainly not the reason for the large variation in the drying times.

The reason could be due to many factors but the main reason is probably because of incoming air to the column had different humidity. The absorption column was not regenerated before every experiment. This results in different equilibrium between the incoming air and the wet solids. A humidified incoming air stream results in a higher equilibrium liquid content in the solid. Beyond this stage the drying stopped. The process is very difficult to analyze since the moisture in the air is an additional solvent

Another important reason for the differences could be the scale of the experimental setup. To obtain reproducible results a larger scale should be used.

Drying process in the column

According to the temperature profiles curves, shown in appendix D, the drying experiments are mainly performed isothermally, except for the beginning of the drying, where the temperature fall some degrees.

Theoretically the drying should be isothermal until the seeds are totally dried, except for the very beginning. Since the entrance of the air is in the bottom of the column, the seeds close to the bottom are the first to be dried and the air becomes saturated before the outlet. A front that separates the wet, saturated upper part with the dry lower part rise through the column as the drying proceeds. When the front reaches the top of the column, and all seeds are dry, the temperature of the out coming gas flow rises as no liquid phase is present in the warmer incoming air flow and no energy is demanded for evaporation.

When the seeds are placed in the equipment and the drying starts the temperature at the inlet of the column decreases. This temperature drop occurs when the hot, unsaturated air stream meets the colder liquid phase within the flakes. The energy in the air stream is not enough to evaporate the liquid, and energy is therefore taken from the flakes. The temperature of the flakes falls and heat is transferred from the column walls to the flakes, while the temperature of the walls decreases, and cools the incoming air flow, which results in that the temperature of the incoming air flow is reduced.

Measurement of the out coming gas concentration during drying

To measure outlet concentrations with interferometer gives information of the out coming gas composition at different times. With that information it is possible to know the remaining moisture content and the drying rate, for each separate component in the mixture, at any time during the drying. This is useful data for simulations of the process.

Unfortunately these measurements did not succeed. Desirable the concentration curve should have started at zero the moment the drying began, instantly increase up to a maximum, and then as the drying proceeds gradually decrease until zero again.

During the three first drying experiments, the scanning functioned well, except for that the very first measurements in each experiment that was impossible to measure. The variations in concentration of the solvents passing the scanner were too high, which resulted in peaks in the beginning of the drying where the concentration is much higher than in the end. At all times more methanol than hexane were detected by the spectrophotometer, independent of solvent ratio, see diagrams 7.4-7.6.

Diagram 7.4: Measurements of the out coming gas concentration during drying. The seeds were leached for 10 hours, flake thickness was 2 mm and the solvent ratio of hexane and methanol was 1:1.

Diagram 7.5: Measurements of the out coming gas concentration during drying. The seeds were leached for 10 hours, flake thickness was 2 mm and the solvent ratio of hexane and methanol was 1:2.

Diagram 7.6: Measurements of the out coming gas concentration during drying. The seeds were leached for 10 hours, flake thickness was 2 mm and the solvent ratio of hexane and methanol was 2:1.

In the fourth experiment a small piece of neem seed, somehow ended up inside the spectrophotometer and destroyed the measurements. The reason for the destroyed results was not detected until long time after all experiments were ended. All measurements of the out coming gas concentration, even the destroyed ones, are shown in appendix E.

8 Conclusions

The parameters chosen to be studied in the leaching part of this thesis were all shown to have a great influence of the yield of insecticide components, but the influence of solvent ratio was the most important one. It was shown that more methanol than hexane had to be used to obtain a large yield of insecticide compounds. The yield of oil was mainly influenced by the flake thickness.

The highest yield of insecticide in this thesis was reached when 2 mm seeds were leached during 30 hours, using a volume ratio of hexane and methanol of 1 to 3, and a total volume of solvents of 400 ml. This experiment was performed four times and the average yield of insecticide compounds was 18.55 percent. This is a higher percent yield compared to both the batch-wise process and the two-step process.

Leaching with the polar- non polar solvent mixture, compared to the batch-wise process and the two-step process, seems to be a more effective alternative when considering both yield of insecticide compounds and total process time.

Leaching with the polar- non polar solvent mixture compared to the batch-wise process and the two-step process, results in a higher yield of insecticide compounds in a shorter total process time, using flake thickness of 2 mm. For the smaller flake thickness, 0.7 mm, 2 percent units lower yield of insecticide compounds were reached in half the total process time compared to the two-step process, but the results had a wide range because a white wax appeared and made the separation after leaching very difficult. For this reason the 0.7 mm flakes were not leached for more than 20 hours.

In the drying part of the thesis obvious conclusions are difficult to make. What can be said is that the temperature of the incoming air flow has influence on the process. A higher temperature results in shorter drying time and faster drying rate at certain moisture content. Conclusions about the drying time or the drying rate are not possible to make from the results of the experiments. The variations in drying time are too large and the drying rate seems to be independent of the conditions of the previous leaching step. To get reliable and reproducible results from drying experiments the scale of the experimental setup should be increased.

The measurements of the out coming gas concentration during drying did not succeed desirable. The variations in concentration of the solvents passing the scanner were too high, which resulted in peaks in the beginning of the drying where the concentration is much higher than in the end. By that important data from the beginning of the experiments were not possible to get. In the fourth experiment small fragments of neem seeds ended up inside the spectrophotometer. This was not detected until long time after all experiments were ended.

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10 Nomenclature

a	specific area	$[\text{m}^2/\text{m}^3]$
c_l	concentration of solvent in liquid phase	$[\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3]$
c_p	heat capacity	$[\text{kJ}/\text{kg}, \text{K}]$
C	concentration	$[\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3]$
D	dispersion coefficient	$[\text{m}^2/\text{s}]$
D_H	thermal diffusivity	$[\text{m}^2/\text{s}]$
D_L	liquid diffusivity	$[\text{m}^2/\text{s}]$
h	heat transfer coefficient	$[\text{W}/\text{m}^2, \text{K}]$
h_D	mass transfer coefficient	$[\text{m}/\text{s}]$
H	height of bed	$[\text{m}]$
k	conductivity	$[\text{kJ}/\text{m}, \text{s}]$
L	length of flake	$[\text{m}]$
m_s	mass of dried flakes	$[\text{kg}]$
M	molar weight	$[\text{kg}/\text{kmol}]$
M_w	molar weight	$[\text{kg}/\text{kmol}]$
N	molar flux	$[\text{kmol}/\text{m}^2, \text{s}]$
N_w	molar flux	$[\text{kmol}/\text{m}^2, \text{s}]$
P_w	pressure	$[\text{N}/\text{m}^2]$
q	heat transfer	$[\text{kJ}/\text{m}^2, \text{s}]$
Q	energy of the solvent vapour added to the gas stream	$[\text{kJ}/\text{m}^3, \text{s}]$
R	gas constant	$[\text{kJ}/\text{kmol}, \text{K}]$
R_i	solvent vapour added to the gas stream	$[\text{kmol}/\text{m}^3, \text{s}]$
S	dimensionless moisture content	$[-]$
t	time	$[\text{s}]$
T	temperature	$[\text{K}]$
u	liquid content	$[-]$
v	gas velocity	$[\text{m}/\text{s}]$
V	volume	$[\text{m}^3]$
x	length	$[\text{m}]$
y	fraction	$[-]$
z	height	$[\text{m}]$

Greek letters

ρ	density	$[\text{kg}/\text{m}^3]$
ε	porosity	$[-]$
Γ	dimensionless dispersion coefficient	$[-]$
Γ_H	dimensionless thermal diffusivity in gas phase	$[-]$
λ	heat of vaporization	$[\text{kJ}/\text{kmol}]$
Θ	dimensionless temperature	$[-]$

τ	dimensionless liquid diffusivity	[-]
τ_H	dimensionless thermal diffusivity in the flakes	[-]
ξ	dimensionless length	[-]
Ψ	dimensionless height	[-]

Subscripts

A	substance
b	bulk
Bm	Logarithmic mean value
g	gas phase
i	component
in	inlet
l	liquid phase
P	particle/flake
s	surface
T	total
0	initial

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